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Postcolonial Identity And Cultural Memory In Adee T. Giwa's *I'd rather die!* A Critical Analytical Analysis

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a postcolonial analysis of Audee T. Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!*, exploring how the novel interrogates the lingering effects of colonialism on identity and cultural memory. Through the lens of postcolonial theory, the analysis examines how Giwa portrays the struggles of marginalized individuals grappling with the legacies of imperialism, both in their personal lives and within broader sociopolitical contexts. Themes of resistance, agency and decolonization are central to the narrative, as characters confront issues of cultural displacement, economic oppression and the search for autonomy. By situating *I'd Rather Die!* within postcolonial discourse, this study highlights Giwa's contribution to the ongoing dialogue about identity, nationhood and the power struggles inherent in postcolonial societies.

Keywords: colonialism, identity, cultural memory

INTRODUCTION

This paper analyses Audee T. Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!* under the requirements of postcolonial theory with a focus on the idea of mimicry. The story is set in a postcolonial African society, and has succeeded in analogizing the friction between the colonizer and the colonized.

Theoretical Framework

For the purposes of the study of literature, the most relevant concern of postcolonial thought has been the decentralization of western culture and its values. Seen from the perspective of a postcolonial world, it has been the major works of thought of Western Europe and American Culture that have dominated philosophy and critical theory as well as works of literature throughout a large part of the world, especially those areas which were formerly under colonial rule.

The subject matter of postcolonial literature is marked by its concern for ambiguity or loss of identity. Written by culturally displaced people, it investigates "the clash of cultures in which one deems itself to be superior and imposes its own practices on the less powerful one" (Dobie 207). Its writers examine their histories, question how they should respond to the changes they see around them, and wonder what their society will become. They recognize in themselves the old culture and the new, elements of the native one and the imposed one. The result is writing that is critical of the conquerors and promotional about its own ideologies.

However, as a theoretical framework, and this is our primary concern here, “postcolonial criticism seeks to understand the operations—politically, socially, culturally, and psychologically—of colonialist and anticolonialist ideologies” (Tyson 418). For example, a good deal of postcolonial criticism analyzes the ideological forces that, on the one hand, pressed the colonized to internalize the colonizers’ values and, on the other hand, promoted the resistance of colonized peoples against their oppressors, a resistance that is as old as colonialism itself. And as we’ll see, because colonialist and anticolonialist ideologies can be present in any literary text, a work doesn’t have to be categorized as postcolonial for us to be able to use postcolonial criticism to analyze it.

Ashcroft et al. and Bennita Parry observe that since the colonised is constructed within the colonialism’s disabling discourse of for a reformed other, Bhabha’s idea of mimicry is simply a parody of the colonialist desire. Therefore, “the success of colonial appropriation depends on a proliferation of inappropriate objects...so that mimicry is at once resemblance and menace” (Bhabha 86).

According to David Carter “Bhabha argues that the interaction between colonizer and colonised leads to the fusion of cultural norms, which confirms the colonial power but also, in its mimicry, threatens to destabilise it” (117). This is possible because the identity of the coloniser is inherently unstable, existing in an isolated expatriate situation. The coloniser’s identity exists by virtue of its difference. It materialises only when in direct contact with the colonised.

Raman Selden et al. argue that

Bhabha probes the (psychic) mechanisms of this process of ‘re-presentation’ to tease out the ‘ambivalence’ of a project that produces colonial subjects which are ‘*almost the same but not quite*’ (and later, ‘*almost the same but not white*’): from the ‘colonial encounter between the white presence and its black semblance, there emerges the question of the ambivalence of mimicry as the problematic of colonial subjection’ (222).

The obligation on the part of the colonized to mirror back an image of the colonizer produces neither identity nor difference, only a version of a ‘presence’ that the colonized subject can only assume ‘partially’. Thus the ‘mimic man’ who occupies the impossible space between cultures is the effect of a flawed colonial mimesis in which to be Anglicized, is emphatically not to be English. Occupying also the precarious area between mimicry and mockery, the mimic man is therefore iconic both of the enforcement of colonial authority and its ‘strategic failure.

Myriad possibilities for hybrid identity formation spring from the very ethnic, racial, and religious differences that delimit and destabilize colony and postcolony alike. Bhabha’s highly influential *Location of Culture* defined colonial mimicry as “the sign of a double articulation; a complex strategy of reform, regulation and discipline, which ‘appropriates’ the Other as it visualizes power. Mimicry is also the sign of the inappropriate, however, a difference or recalcitrance which coheres the dominant strategic function of colonial power, intensifies surveillance, and poses an imminent threat to both ‘normalized’ knowledges and disciplinary powers” (qtd. in Castle 139). Mimicry is double-edged; it is the sign of a colonial discourse that desires a “reformed, recognizable Other” but it is also the means by which the colonized subject challenges that discourse.

One of the most persistent prejudices underlying the production of the texts of the metropolitan canon is that only certain categories of experience are capable of being rendered as ‘literature’. This privileging of particular types of experience denies access to the world for the writer subject to a dominating colonial culture. It works in a complicated and reciprocal way, both denying value to the post-colonial experience itself, as ‘unworthy’ of literature, and preventing postcolonial texts from engaging with that experience. The result is that “the post-colonial writer is consigned to a world of mimicry and imitation, since he is forced to write about material which lies at one remove from the significant experiences of the post-colonial world” (Ashcroft et al. 87).

The dominant discourse constructs Otherness in such a way that it always contains a trace of ambivalence or anxiety about its own authority. In order to maintain authority over the Other in a colonial situation, “imperial discourse strives to delineate the Other as radically different from the self, yet at the same time it must maintain sufficient identity with the Other to valorize control over it” (Ashcroft et al. 102). The

Other can, of course, only be constructed out of the archive of ‘the self’, yet the self must also articulate the Other as inescapably different. Otherness can thus only be produced by a continual process of what Bhabha calls ‘repetition and displacement’ and this instigates an ambivalence at the very site of imperial authority and control. Thus there is a kind of built-in resistance in the construction of any dominant discourse – and opposition is an almost inevitable effect of its construction of cultural difference. Of course, what such authority least likes, and what presents it with its greatest threat, is any reminder of such ambivalence.

Lois Tyson provides some questions postcolonial critics ask when analyzing a text (Tyson 431):

1. How does the literary text, explicitly or allegorically, represent various aspects of colonial oppression? Special attention is often given to those areas where political and cultural oppression overlap, as it does, for example, in the colonizers’ control of language, communication, and knowledge in colonized countries.
2. What does the text reveal about the problematics of postcolonial identity, including the relationship between personal and cultural identity and such issues as double consciousness and hybridity?
3. What does the text reveal about the politics and/or psychology of anticolonialist resistance? For example, what does the text suggest about the ideological, political, social, economic, or psychological forces that promote or inhibit resistance? How does the text suggest that resistance can be achieved and sustained by an individual or a group?
4. What does the text reveal about the operations of cultural difference—the ways in which race, religion, class, gender, sexual orientation, cultural beliefs, and customs combine to form individual identity—in shaping our perceptions of ourselves, others, and the world in which we live? *Othering* might be one area of analysis here.
5. How does the text respond to or comment on the characters, topics, or assumptions of a canonized (colonialist) work?
6. Are there meaningful similarities among the literatures of different postcolonial populations? One might compare, for example, the literatures of native peoples from different countries whose land was invaded by colonizers, the literatures of white settler colonies in different countries, or the literatures of different populations in the African diaspora. Or one might compare literary works from all three of these categories in order to investigate, for example, if the experience of colonization creates some common elements of cultural identity that outweigh differences in race and nationality.

Postcolonial analysis of *I’d Rather Die!*

I’d Rather Die! is a love story revealing how socio-economy status affects relationships, and the life of all those involved. This relationship is expressed in action, thought, dialogue and gesture of the characters. Fatimah has found love in a young fellow, called Mohammed, but is being played at by an elderly man, Alhaji Maikudi, who wants Fatimah for procreation, and who, with his wealth, feels he rules the world, and her father Mal Umar, who would do anything for money. Alhaji Maikudi, after meeting Fatimah in a bus on his way home, concludes in his mind that he must have Fatimah by all cost

The narrator of the text states what motivates Alhaji Maikudi’s choice of another wife. Through the use of interior monologue, irony and satire, the author presents the thoughts of the character in sequence, and in summary, a background knowledge of the character’s life Alhaji Maikudi. The narrator, exposes the reality of othering a character by telling the readers that Alhaji Maikudi conveniently forgets that he had married: “all his wives as virgin” (73). Alhaji Maikudi wishes to have Fatimah at all costs whether or not she agrees. This similarity of colonial oppression is presented to the reader through Maikudi’s aim of contracting another marriage and alongside the view that in Africa’s cultural set-up, the woman is conveniently blamed for childlessness.

Through the character of Alhaji Maikudi, the author presents the story of a man who takes advantage of religion, financial status and culture to the detriment of others around him. Religiously, he takes advantage of polygamy and practice it without concern or fairness. This element of colonial oppression helps the reader understand why the character is behaving in a particular way and why he has reacted to a

particular situation of an action. Whereas financially, he uses his wealth to oppress all around him by planning his move in a sequential order.

Through the roles the characters played, the author presents the themes in the novel. For example, through patriarchy, we see the system of colonial oppression and anticolonialist resistance, when the heroine states: "No, I won't marry him father! I won't. I would rather leave this house and go to any whore-house in town to live. Or better still, I'd rather die!" (91). Mallam Umar finds it strange that his daughter will disobey him in his choice of a husband for her, as this is the first time she shouts at him. The subject of this plot is Fatimah, who bluntly refuses the offer of marriage to an older man.

Mallam Umar laments the condition of teachers and meagre salary they have to eke out living with. The readers can see a graphic, descriptive, arresting suggestive opening in the story. In line with the opening of the story, one sees why Hamza referred to Mallam Umar as: "ido kwabo: "He has his eyes on the easy dough" (89). And Amina's stream of consciousness describes her husband in line with his friend's opinion: "When they said that squeezing water out of stone was easier than money out of Umar" (12). At the same time, the reader may try to comprehend Mal. Umar's plight because he earns so little and lives in a "dilapidated looking house" (8), has no good means of transportation: "His rickety old bicycle was becoming a burden. It gave an irritating 'kyat' sound. He was tired, hungry and exhausted" (7). The author's language is full of figurative language, proverbs, idioms, irony, humour and satire, as he used the role of Mal. Umar to depict the social status of a teacher in Nigeria and the oppression of so called "Alhajis" in the society.

Alhaji Maikudi's motive for marrying a girl who is barely seventeen years-old continues to land him in series of problems both physical, psychological and emotional. The author shows the reader a mimicry of anticolonialist resistance. Physically, he is bitten by Fatimah, when he attempts to rape her: "His middle finger was descending downwards, he was so overcome with excitement when suddenly she caught the short fat finger between her teeth and compressed them mercilessly. 'Wayyoooo' Alhaji yowled" (130-1). Mal Umar plays an active role in the story as a subject and helper. For the family to feed, he needs to drop money for the foodstuff to be bought or taken on credit. Mallam Umar performs the role of the coloniser because he steers and directs events in his household as he wished. His role makes things happen. He is the father and main provider in the home. When at home, he directs food stuff to be bought:

Run as fast as you can, commanded Mallam Umar (to Ibrahim), to Maishinkafa's house and buy three mudus of rice, a bottle of palm oil and a cupful of salt"

Am I to buy all these with pebbles, Baba?

Tell her she would get her money over the weekend

Thirty minutes later, after Mallam Umar had finished saying his afternoon prayers, Amina came into the room carrying three plates one on top of the other, without a tray (11-12).

Amina, his wife plays the role of the other because she is influenced, modified and stopped or permitted to go ahead: "She sat and watched him eat" (12). She plays the role of a submissive wife to Mallam Umar and a mother to Fatimah and Ibrahim.

To add local colour to the composition of the text, the use of the formerly colonised local language is written in italics and translated in English. For example, "the zaure, as the outer room (8), what in English is called living, sitting room or parlour, for welcoming and entertaining visitors, for consummation of the marriage shigan daki (the supposed day for official consummation of the marriage)" (149). Other words/phrases/clauses are: "Maishinkafa" (11), "Babban Dodo" (47), "A kawo kudi" (69), "Mutanen gida duk lafiya?" (86), "Kofan doka" (152), "Barka da zuwa" (152), "Assalamu alaikum" (15), "gari" (63) all to reflect the author's level of language placing him as an African, Nigerian and Hausa, with the knowledge of Arabic to show he indeed is well read and has moved around.

CONCLUSION

The novel has a well-conceived structure based on conventional pattern, and implies the process of mimicry that plays between the formerly colonised and coloniser. The sequence of events and the narrative arrangement in the novel is superb and placed in chronological sequence of time. It is essentially a postcolonial document. Telling a story from several points of view has obvious possibilities for representing characters in depth, or the ambiguities of the postcolonial condition. It adds verisimilitude, contributes to large-scale ironies, and perhaps gives the relief of variety.

The author's use of multiple roles played by a character gives concrete evidence that the postcolonial individual has many facets with direct and indirect characterisation for specific purpose and message in a unique way thereby making the narration stand out. Audee T. Giwa uses a major character by allowing Mallam Umar, an unsociable, irritating and stingy but inoffensive man, to describe his opening. He then invites the wife, Amina, who is presented as a lazy and a dirty woman, using the description of the house and bringing in Mallam Umar's son who happens to be a humorous character.

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